

Supplement to: Non-maximizing policies that fulfill multi-criterion aspirations in expectation

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1 Clipping instead of shrinking

1.1 While propagating action-aspirations to state-aspirations

In section 4.1 of the main text, we define shifted copies $\mathcal{X}_{s'}$ of the action-aspiration \mathcal{E} , which would be appropriate candidates for subsequent state-aspirations if not for the fact that they are not necessarily subsets of $\mathcal{V}^{\mathcal{R}}(s')$. In the main text, we resolve this by shrinking $\mathcal{X}_{s'}$ until it fits.

An alternative approach is *clipping*, where we calculate the sets $\mathcal{X}_{s'}$ and simply set $\mathcal{E}_{s'} = \mathcal{X}_{s'} \cap \mathcal{V}^{\mathcal{R}}(s')$.

1.2 While choosing actions and action-aspirations

In section 4.2.(iii) of the main text, we shift the aspiration set in a certain direction y and shrink it until it fits into the action feasibility reference simplices $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$.

Clipping is also an alternative here, as illustrated in figure 1. To use clipping instead of shrinking, algorithm 2 of the main text can be modified by replacing the procedure SHRINKASPIRATION with the procedure CLIPASPIRATION defined here:

Algorithm 1 Clipping variation for algorithm 2 of main text.

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1: procedure CLIPASPIRATION( $a_i, i$ )
2:    $v \leftarrow V^{\pi_i}(s)$  if  $i > 0$ , else  $C(\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i))$   $\triangleright$  vertex or center of target
3:    $y \leftarrow v - x$   $\triangleright$  shifting direction
4:    $r \leftarrow \max\{r \geq 0 : x - ry \in \mathcal{E}\}$   $\triangleright$  distance from boundary point  $b$  of  $\mathcal{E}$  to  $x$ 
5:    $\ell \leftarrow \min\{\ell \geq 0 : x + \ell y \in \mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)\}$   $\triangleright$  distance from  $x$  to reference simplex
6:    $\ell' \leftarrow \max\{\ell' \geq 0 : x + \ell' y \in \mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)\}$   $\triangleright$  dist. from  $x$  to far bdry. of ref. simplex
7:    $z \leftarrow \min(r + \ell, \ell')y$   $\triangleright$  shifting vector
8:   return  $(z + \mathcal{E}_s) \cap \mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$   $\triangleright$  shift and clip (nonempty)
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The direction y is determined as in the shrinking variant. Next, we determine by linear programming the outermost point $b \in \mathcal{E}$ lying on the ray from x in the direction $-y$. \mathcal{E} is shifted in direction y , stopping either when the shifted boundary point b (and thus generally a large part of \mathcal{E}) enters the reference simplex $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$, or when the shifted center x exits $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$. The appropriate shifting distance can be computed using linear programming. This is done in lines 5 to 7 of Algorithm 1. Finally, the shifted copy of \mathcal{E} is clipped to $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$ by uniting their H -representations to get \mathcal{E}_{a_i} , i.e., consider the set of all hyperplanes on which a facet of either \mathcal{E} or $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$ lies. Then the vertices of \mathcal{E}_{a_i} are computed from the resulting H -representation. The sets \mathcal{E}_{a_i} are nonempty because the ray from x in direction y intersects $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a_i)$.

Fig. 1. Construction of action-aspirations \mathcal{E}_a from state-aspiration \mathcal{E} and reference simplices $\mathcal{V}^{\mathcal{R}}(s)$ and $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a)$ by shifting and clipping. See main text for details.

1.3 Advantages and disadvantages of clipping

Clipping instead of shrinking has the advantage that it produces strictly larger propagated aspiration sets, which might be desirable as discussed in section 3 of the main text.

However, clipping changes the shape of aspiration sets, adding up to $d + 1$ defining hyperplanes at each step, and requiring recomputation of the set of vertices which may become combinatorially large. Therefore, we expect the complexity of the clipping variant to be worse than shrinking, though we have not studied it formally.

2 Alternate version of action selection/local policy computation

Some action selection criteria which we may wish to use are “farsighted” and require knowing the future behavior of the policy as well. Algorithm 2 of the main text does not provide this information, as it samples candidate actions a_i first before determining the probabilities with which to mix them. The algorithm 2 presented here is an adaptation which does provide the full local policy before sampling from it to choose the action taken. It does so by replacing the sampling in lines 4 and 7 of the original algorithm by a computation of the respective probabilities. Instead of solving the linear program in line 6 of main-text algorithm 2 for each of the at most $|\mathcal{A}|^{d+2}$ many candidate action combinations (a_0, \dots, a_{d+1}) , line 7 uses a single linear program invocation manipulating the average action-aspirations for each direction, $\mathbb{E}_{a_i \sim \pi_i} \mathcal{E}_{a_i}$. This ensures complexity remains linear in $|\mathcal{A}|$. A solution to this linear program exists since $\mathbb{E}_{a_i \sim \pi_i} \mathcal{E}_{a_i} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_s + \mathbb{E}_{a_i \sim \pi_i} z_{a_i}$ and $\mathbb{E}_{a_i \sim \pi_i} z_{a_i}$ is a positive multiple of $V^{\pi_i}(s) - x$; the proof of Lemma 2 of the main text is readily adapted. Finally, the loop in lines 8 to 11 is necessary as one same action may lie in two distinct directional action sets $\mathcal{A}_i \neq \mathcal{A}_j$.

Algorithm 2 Local policy computation (“clip” and “shrink” variants)

Require: Reference simplex vertices $V^{\pi_i}(s)$, $Q^{\pi_i}(s, a)$; state s ; state-aspiration \mathcal{E}_s .

- 1: $x \leftarrow C(\mathcal{E}_s)$, $\mathcal{E}' \leftarrow \mathcal{E}_s - x$ \triangleright center, shape
- 2: **for** $i = 0, \dots, d + 1$ **do**
- 3: $\mathcal{A}_i \leftarrow \text{DirectionalActionSet}(i)$
- 4: $\pi_i \leftarrow \text{CandidateActionDistribution}(\mathcal{A}_i)$ \triangleright any probability distribution on \mathcal{A}_i
- 5: **for** $a_i \in \mathcal{A}_i$ **do**
- 6: $\mathcal{E}_{a_i} \leftarrow \text{ClipAspiration}(a_i, i)$ or $\text{ShrinkAspiration}(a_i, i)$ \triangleright action-aspiration
- 7: solve linear program $p_0 = \max!$, $\sum_{i=0}^{d+1} p_i \mathbb{E}_{a_i \sim \pi_i} \mathcal{E}_{a_i} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_s$ for $p \in \Delta(\{0, \dots, d + 1\})$
- 8: initialize $\pi \equiv 0$
- 9: **for** $i = 0, \dots, d + 1$ **do** \triangleright collect probabilities across directions
- 10: **for** $a_i \in \mathcal{A}_i$ **do**
- 11: $\pi(a_i, \mathcal{E}_{a_i}) \leftarrow \pi(a_i, \mathcal{E}_{a_i}) + p_i \pi_i(a_i)$
- return** π \triangleright local policy

3 Video of an example run

In the video accessible at the anonymous download link https://mega.nz/file/gUgTzZqB#Co21aSoKQAo7PjeR9_kzxzquHdjlnav0qjp9wKX3NRU, we illustrate the propagation of aspirations from states to actions in one episode of a simple gridworld environment.

In that environment, the agent starts at the central position (3,3) in a 5-by-5 rectangular grid, can move up, down, left, right, or pass in each of 10 time steps,

and gets a Delta $f(s, a, s') = g(s')$ that only depends on its next position s' on the grid. The values $g(s')$ are iid 2-d standard normal random values.

In each time-step, the black dashed triangle is the current state’s reference simplex $\mathcal{V}^{\mathcal{R}}(s)$, the blue triangles are the five candidate actions’ reference simplices $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a)$, the red square is the state-aspiration \mathcal{E} , the dotted lines connect its center, the red dot, with the vertices of $\mathcal{V}^{\mathcal{R}}(s)$ or with the centers of the sets $\mathcal{Q}^{\mathcal{R}}(s, a)$, and the green squares are the resulting action-aspirations \mathcal{E}_a .

The coordinate system is “moving along” with the received Delta, so that aspirations of consecutive steps can be compared more easily. In other words, the received Delta $R_t = \sum_{t'=0}^{t-1} f(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1})$ is added to all vertices so that, e.g., the vertices of the back dashed triangle are shown at positions $R_t + V^{\pi_i}(s_t)$ rather than $V^{\pi_i}(s_t)$.

This run uses the linear volume shrinking schedule $r_{\max}(s) = (1 - 1/T(s))^{1/d}$. As one can see, the state-aspirations indeed shrink smoothly towards a final point aspiration, which spends the initial amount of “freedom” rather evenly across states. This way, the agent manages to avoid drift in this case, so that the eventual point aspiration is still inside the initial aspiration set.

4 Numerical evidence for reference policy selection complexity

In order to study the number of trials needed to find the $d + 1$ directions that define suitable reference policies for the definition of reference simplices, we performed numerical experiments with binary-tree-shaped environments of the following type.

Each environment has 10 time steps, each state has two actions, each action can lead to two different successor states, leading to 4^{10} many terminal states. Deltas $f(s, a, s')$ are iid uniform variates in $[0, 1]^d$. The initial aspiration is $(5, \dots, 5)$.

For each $d \in \{1, \dots, 8\}$, we perform 1000 independent simulations and find that the average number k of trials until $\mathcal{E}_0 \in \text{conv}\{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$ is below $2d + 1$ for all tested d .